

Report on aspects of outdoor lighting

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Paola Iacomussi
INRIM

Giuseppe Rossi
INRIM

Michela Radis
INRIM

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Author(s)	:	Paola Iacomussi INRIM Giuseppe Rossi INRIM Michela Radis INRIM
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About the EMRP

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About the EMRP JRP "Metrology for Solid State Lighting"

In the EMRP Joint Research Project (JRP) "Metrology for Solid State Lighting", the following partners cooperate to create a European infrastructure for the traceable measurement of solid state lighting: VSL (Coordinator), Aalto, CMI, CSIC, EJPD, INRIM, IPQ, LNE, MKEH, NPL, PTB, SMU, SP, Trescal, CCR, TU Ilmenau and Université Paul Sabatier. See <http://www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk/> for more information.

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SUMMARY

This report considers the use of LED in outdoor lighting, with specific reference to road lighting where LED luminaires show the most interesting performances. A comparison between LED road luminaires and traditional sources luminaires from the point of view of normative performances (illuminance and luminance requirements), installation influences and light pollution, considering both the case of a single luminaire and light plant contribution, is provided. No reference is done to spectral peculiarities of SSL because outside the scope of this report

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	INTRODUCTION	3
2	RELEVANT STANDARDS ABOUT OUTDOOR LIGHTING.....	4
2.1	Main parameters considered in the relevant documents	4
3	THE CASE OF ROAD LIGHTING	1
4	CASE STUDY: ROAD LIGHTING METAL HALIDE VS LED INSTALLATIONS	3
4.1	Electrical parameters characterization in lab	5
4.1	Photometric parameters characterization on site.....	5
4.2	Installation influences.....	6
4.3	Measurement of installation lighting factor.....	10
4.4	Road lighting vs sky luminance.....	11
5	CONCLUSIONS	14
6	REFERENCES	15

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Lighting installation with metal halide luminaire with flat closure	3
Figure 2 Lighting installation with metal halide luminaire with curved closure	4
Figure 3 Lighting installation with LED luminaire with curved closure	4
Figure 4 Lighting installation with LED luminaires with flat closure	5
Figure 5 Illuminance on the road surface, Metal Halide curved closure, installation A.....	7
Figure 6 Illuminance on the road surface, Metal Halide curved closure, installation B.....	7
Figure 7 Illuminance on the road surface, LED flat closure, installation A.....	8
Figure 8 Illuminance on the road surface, LED flat closure, installation B.....	8
Figure 9 Illuminance on the road surface, LED curved closure, installation A.....	9
Figure 10 Illuminance on the road surface, LED curved closure, installation B.....	9

LIST OF SYMBOLS

C_{γ} angles used in the CIE C_{γ} reference system for luminous intensity spatial distribution of luminaires

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CCT	Correlated Colour Temperature
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIE	Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
IES	Illuminating Engineering Society
IESNA	Illuminating Engineering Society of North America
JRP	Joint Research Project
LED	Lighting Emitting Diode
NMI	National Measurement Institute
q_r	Installation luminance factor
SSL	Solid State Lighting
UNI	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione (Italian Standard Organization)

1 INTRODUCTION

Outdoor lighting includes road lighting and general lighting for outdoor, like city beautyfication or lighting for outdoor work places. The main interest is focused on road lighting because the numbers involved: EU estimated the EU27 consumption for road lighting is about 4,73% of tertiary sector consumptions (in 2007) [1], while stakeholder ENEA estimated the Italian consumption for public lighting the 12,6% of National consumptions [2] (in 2012). The aim of road lighting is the safety of the citizens and generally of the traffic, a social objective which is however associated with a contradictory result: energy consumption with emission of green house gases which increases the atmospheric pollution and consequently impairs the health of the citizens, at least in the countries which use fossil fuels for the generation of electricity and the increase of artificial sky luminance at night with, consequently, stars visibility reduction. EU is aware of the problem of energy consumption, and in the last years face it with different directives, focused on the problem. The EU approach is:

- To labell and standardize product information
- To adopt the minimum energy performance standards (ecodesign requirements)

For lighting, Commision Regulation implemeted the Ecodesign directive (2005/32/EC), in particular for LED lighting implemented the directive 2009/125/EC, while directive 2009/245/EC is in force since April 2009. Directive 245 gives prescription about lighting pollution and performances for energy saving.

Additional savings can be achieved through a careful design of lighting installations associated with efficient lighting sources and luminaires. Last but not least, the environmental compatibility, which enters more and more into the picture, benefits from energy savings.

2 RELEVANT STANDARDS ABOUT OUTDOOR LIGHTING

Available EN standards for outdoor lighting are listed in Table 1. Outdoor lighting includes outdoor work places lighting, road lighting, city beautification, and private outside lighting usually not regulated by normative, exception for Italy about lighting pollution rules. City Beautification (Flood lighting), has purely aesthetic and decorative purpose, no standard is available because is essentially managed at town level using indications provided by relevant CIE document about it [2] ENEA research http://www.enea.it/it/Ricerca_sviluppo/documenti/ricerca-di-sistema-elettrico/illuminazione-pubblica/18a-pres.-lumiere.pdf

[3] IEC 62471:2006/CIE S 009:2006 Photobiological safety of lamps and lamp systems, IEC

[4] EN 62471:2008, Photobiological Safety of lamps and lamp systems

[5] IES Position Statement PS–03-10, Effects of exterior lighting on human health, 2010

[6]. But Flood lighting gives its contribution to lighting pollution and energy consumptions too. For these reasons in available documents for lighting pollution reduction usually flood lighting is limited in time (usually is switched off at late night). Table 1 includes also an Italian standard about the limitation of lighting pollution due to outdoor lighting plants. This documents is a peculiar one because is the only standard available in Europe about the lighting pollution. European regulations take in account of lighting pollution indirectly through documents like directive on energy consumption and Standard EN12464-2.

Table 1 Main EU standard regarding outdoor lighting

Document	Title
CEN/TR 13201-1:2004	Road lighting - Part 1: Selection of lighting classes
EN 12193:2007	Light and lighting - Sports lighting
EN 12464-2:2007	Light and lighting - Lighting of work places - Part 2: Outdoor work places
EN 13201-2:2003	Road lighting - Part 2: Performance requirements
EN 13201-3:2003	Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance
EN 13201-3:2003/AC:200	Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance
EN 13201-4:2003	Road lighting - Part 4: Methods of measuring lighting performance
prCEN/TR 13201-1 rev	Road lighting - Part 1: Selection of lighting classes
prEN 13201-2 rev	Road lighting - Part 2: Performance requirements
prEN 13201-3 rev	Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance
prEN 13201-4 rev	Road lighting - Part 4: Methods of measuring lighting performance
prEN 13201-5	Road lighting - Part 5: Energy efficiency requirements
FprEN 12464-2	Light and lighting - Lighting of work places - Outdoor work places
UNI 10819	Outdoor lighting - Requirement for the limitation of upward flux

2.1 Main parameters considered in the relevant documents

The main parameters considered in available outdoor lighting documents are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Relevant parameters in available documents

Document	Parameter	Value	Specific Requirements	Suggestions
EN 12464-2	Maintained Illuminance on the task area, E_m	5 - 500 lx		
	Maximum GR limits, GR_L	40 - 55		
	Minimum Illuminance Uniformity, U_0	0.10 - 0,50		
	Minimum Colour Rendering Indexes, R_a	20 - 60		
	Luminance distribution		well balanced	
	Illuminance on the surroundings area	100 - 20 lx		
	Uniformity of surroundings	1/10 of task area		
	Veiling reflection		to avoid	
	Reflection glare		to avoid	
Flicker, stroboscopic		to avoid		
Obstrusive light		Depending on the environmental zone or road class	Expressed in terms of ULR, illuminance, luminance, luminaire intensity and TI Increment	
EN 12193	Color Temperature T_{cp}			
	Maximum permissible deviation of T_{cp}			
	Minimum Colour Rendering Index, R_a			
	Preferred Colour Rendering Index, R_a			
IESNA Guidelines	Illuminance (vertical and horizontal)		no specific requirements, but several suggestion depending on the application are provided	A community responsive design approach is suggested
	Luminance			
	Luminance ratio			
	Brightness			
	Glare			
	Light trespass			
EN 13201	Average road surface luminance (L)	0,3 - 2,0 cd/m ²	provided minimum maintained value depending on the road class	
	Overall uniformity of the luminance (U_0)	0,35 - 0,4	providing minimum value depending on the road class	
	Longitudinal uniformity of the luminance (U_L)	0,4 - 0,7	providing minimum value depending on the road class	
	Threshold increment (TI)	15-Oct	providing maximum value depending on the road class	For installation where TI cannot be calculated, the maximum luminous intensity at different angles is provided
	Surround ratio (SR)	0,5	providing minimum value depending on the road class	
	Average horizontal illuminance (E)	2 - 50 lx	providing minimum value depending on the road class	
	Overall uniformity of the horizontal illuminance (U_0)	0,4	providing minimum value depending on the road class	
	Average hemispherical illuminance (E_{hs})	1 - 5 lx		
	Overall uniformity of the hemispherical illuminance (U_0)	0,15		
Average semi-cylindrical illuminance (E_{sc})	0,5 - 10 lx			

2.2 Effects of exterior lighting on human health

A lot of discussions is on going about the effects of exterior lighting on human health. It is a complex and difficult research, as human health related investigations are, the main problems arise from the extend of the argument, the difficulties in defining short, medium and long term related effects and the available resources. In principle lighting community is aware of the optical radiation related risks. In 2006 IEC published IEC 6247:2006 then adopted by EU in 2008 with standard EN62471:2008. In the original IEC document of 2006 [3], hazard exposure limits are taken from various guidelines supposed to be the best available information. The most interesting and, now, criticized suggestion is that a source with a luminance less than 10^4 cd/m², never exceeds the exposure limits provided in the document. The main parameters affecting the definition of exposure limits values are: pupil diameter, source angular subtense (in relationship with rapid eye movement) and exposure time of fixation necessary to calculate source radiance. In the EU document [4], differently from IEC standard, hazard exposure limits are covered by the Artificial Optical Radiation Directive (2006/25/EC). EN62471:2008 adopts Directive limits, that, unfortunately, are less restrictive than IEC suggestions, especially for the exposure limit.

IES published in 2010 a Position Statement [5] about the effects of exterior lighting on human health, were IES position based on the available results is: “*typical exposures to exterior lighting after sunset have not been shown to lead to cancer or other life-threatening conditions.*”, but also says “ *new spectral weighting functions that are appropriate for characterizing non visual responses to optical radiation are needed*”.

A deep review about safety quality parameters is provided in Deliverable D4.3.6 of this project.

3 THE CASE OF ROAD LIGHTING

We choose to consider in more details the case of road lighting, because involves more electrical consumptions (in Italy public lighting is 12,6% of National consumptions [2]) and for this application SSL lighting is more promising. EU is aware that road lighting needs to:

- assure the safety of the citizens;
- increase the efficiency of all lighting components;
- increase the efficiency of the design of lighting installations;
- reduce the obtrusive light, i.e. the luminous flux which disturbs the citizens and their activities.

The first objective can be realised through the compliance with standards, which are issued in each country.

The second one depends mainly on the light sources, a field where the LEDs can play a major, but also on scientific publications (i.e. CIE Technical Report about mesopic vision [7]) and the adoption of EU directive on ecodesign and energy performances.

In fact SSL luminaires are promising because:

- the white light with a high colour rendering with a better perception of obstacles in peripheral vision at mesopic levels;
- the higher visual comfort of white light;
- the small size and the possibility of an accurate aiming of the light beam, with higher utilisation factors;
- the long life with reduced maintenance costs;
- the luminous efficiencies continuously increasing because of the technological innovation, with foreseen targets higher than high pressure sodium lamps;

In order to verify the last two points on a typical roadlighting installation INRIM with the stakeholder ENEA and AIDI performed a measurement campaign in order to establish:

- the increase of lighting design and installation efficacy;
- the obtrusive light

of a SSL road lighting plant obtained with SSL luminaires respect Metal Halide luminaires.

4 CASE STUDY: ROAD LIGHTING METAL HALIDE VS LED INSTALLATIONS

Four different lighting installations, two with LED luminaires (curved and flat glass closure) and two with Metal Halide luminaires (curved and flat glass closure), were compared in this case study carried out with the participation of stakeholder ENEA. All installations have been set-up on the same test road. Figure 1 to Figure 4 show the installations on the test road.

Figure 1 Lighting installation with metal halide luminaire with flat closure

Figure 2 Lighting installation with metal halide luminaire with curved closure

Figure 3 Lighting installation with LED luminaire with curved closure

Figure 4 Lighting installation with LED luminaires with flat closure

4.1 Electrical parameters characterization in lab

The measured electrical parameters of the luminaires during the characterization in lab are shown in Table 3, with the measured uncertainty values.

Table 3 Measured electrical parameters of the luminaires installed

4.1 Photometric parameters characterization on site

The on site photometric values were acquired following the prescriptions of [9] and shown in Table 4.

The uncertainty values due only to photometric measurements (not considering possible variation of the electrical power source) are $\pm 5 \%$ for illuminance and $\pm 10 \%$ for luminance values.

Table 4 Site-measured parameters

Parameter	Normative grid on site measured			
	Metal Halide		LED	
	flat closure	curved closure	flat closure	curved closure
Nominal Pole interdistance [m]	33	37	33	37
Mean illuminance [lx]	15,0	14,0	15,8	14,8
Illuminance Uniformity (min/med) [-]	0,35	0,25	0,39	0,41
Uniformity along central line, right side (min/max) [-]	0,19	0,11	0,28	0,23
Uniformity along central line, left side (min/max) [-]	0,31	0,23	0,38	0,37
Mean Luminance [cd/m ²] right side	1,16	1,14	1,40	1,47
Mean Luminance [cd/m ²] left side	1,29	1,05	1,52	1,51
Overall Uniformity [-] right side	0,38	0,42	0,45	0,41
Overall Uniformity [-] left side	0,35	0,47	0,43	0,46
Longitudinal Uniformity [-] right side	0,56	0,34	0,72	0,71
Longitudinal Uniformity [-] left side	0,54	0,36	0,80	0,68

4.2 Installation influences

In order to evaluate the mechanical installation influences the same luminaires were also installed inside the INRIM premises.

The results are show as isolux graphs in Figure 5 to Figure 9.

Figure 5 Illuminance on the road surface, Metal Halide curved closure, installation A

Figure 6 Illuminance on the road surface, Metal Halide curved closure, installation B

Figure 7 Illuminance on the road surface, LED flat closure, installation A

Figure 8 Illuminance on the road surface, LED flat closure, installation B

Figure 9 Illuminance on the road surface, LED curved closure, installation A

Figure 10 Illuminance on the road surface, LED curved closure, installation B

It is clearly evident how installation set up can influence the lighting performances: lighting design software are able to calculate lighting plant for different installation set up, including tilting angles, and their influences on quality installation parameters and illuminances requirements. But at the installation in situ, the set up is completely different: the luminaire is installed on the pole and no specific alignment references are available to the installer. Usually the installation is made inserting the luminaire on the pole up to framing it at the end of the coupling. The suggestion is to provide additional reference in order to set correctly the tilt angles especially with the so called “pole head” luminaires, i.e. luminaires directly inserted on the pole.

4.3 Measurement of installation lighting factor

The draft version of new part 5 of EN13201, road lighting, about Energy Performances [10], considers the installation lighting factor q_{inst} , defined as:

$$q_{inst} = \frac{Q_{calc}}{Q_0} = \frac{L_{calc}}{E_{calc} Q_0}$$

where:

L_{calc} is the calculated luminance

E_{calc} is the calculated illuminance

Q_0 is the average luminance coefficient of the r-table adopted in luminance calculation, it is a normalising parameter that permits to characterise the energy performances of a lighting installation and/or to compare the performances of different lighting installations independently of the actual value of the luminance coefficient Q_0 for the real road surface, which can be measured or evaluated, but looking only at the performances of the luminaires installed in the plant. It was firstly proposed as road quality factor qr in [11]. The importance of evaluating luminance vs illuminance is confirmed in CIE relevant publication about road surface [8] where it is stated the luminance coefficient of lighting installation Q_R :

$$Q_R = \frac{L_R}{E_R}$$

where:

L_R is the mean road luminance

E_R is the mean road illuminance

Regarding the characterized lighting plant the Q_R values are in Table 5

Table 5 Luminance coefficient of lighting installation

Parameter	Normative grid on site measured			
	Metal Halide		LED	
	flat closure	curved closure	flat closure	curved closure
Luminance coefficient Q_R [sr-1] right side	0,077	0,083	0,089	0,100
Luminance coefficient Q_R [sr-1] left side	0,086	0,076	0,096	0,102

Higher values of Q_R mean higher luminances with less illuminance, and, consequently with less energy consumption, that is clearly achieved with LED luminaires, independently from the electrical power of the luminaires.

If the above values will be compared to Q_0 of road CE2 class (value 0,07) it will be possible through q_{inst} , to compare the performances of installation plants independently from the road light class and design. Not only, but since with lower illuminances the luminous flux reflected by the illuminated surfaces (road, buildings, grass, etc.) will decrease, also the sky luminance will be lower.

Table 6 Installation lighting factor

Parameter	Normative grid on site measured			
	Metal Halide		LED	
	flat closure	curved closure	flat closure	curved closure
Luminance coefficient Q_R [sr-1] right side	0,077	0,083	0,089	0,100
Luminance coefficient Q_R [sr-1] left side	0,086	0,076	0,096	0,102
Installation lighting factor right side [-]	1,10	1,19	1,27	1,43
Installation lighting factor right side [-]	1,23	1,09	1,37	1,46

4.4 Road lighting vs sky luminance

There is no doubt that public lighting disturbs astronomical observation, but also that public lighting is necessary for assuring the safety of the citizens and of the traffic in urban areas. The photometric characteristics of the luminaires, and particularly the luminous flux directly emitted upwards (spill light), and their installation methods are frequently associated with the reduction of the visibility of heavenly bodies, without taking account with the correct weight, that such reduction is mainly due to the luminous flux

reflected by the illuminated surfaces (roads, buildings), that lighting levels are prescribed by national and international norms and that lighting installations are unavoidable. In order to reduce the negative side effects of road lighting for astronomy on one side and energy consumptions on the other, some Italian laws (usually regional laws, driven especially by astronomers associations), EU regulations [12] and technical publications [13] [14] issued in the last decade limited the luminous flux, sometime the luminous intensity, emitted upward by the luminaires (ULOR), considered the sole cause of the artificial sky luminance. But this is not completely true: the artificial luminance of sky is due to upward emission and, especially, reflections by illuminated surfaces.

Luminaires have been characterised in laboratory with a goniophotometer that allows the evaluation of the total emitted flux but also of the emitted flux in the most interesting spherical zones: spherical zone with elevation angle γ $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 100^\circ$ is the most interesting for lighting pollution because the radiation emitted in that angles is very disturbing, while the emitted flux in spherical zones with $88^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 90^\circ$ and $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 92^\circ$ is descriptive of alignment influences. The measured values are shown in Table 7

It is to note that all luminaires have an emitted flux in the spherical zone between elevation angles $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 100^\circ$ included in $0,2\% \leq \Phi_{90-100} \leq 0,015\%$ of the total emitted flux, proof of the optimized design also of the luminaires with curved closure.

Table 7 Luminaires measured luminous flux

Parameter		Laboratory charact. @ nominal electrical power							
		Metal Halide				LED			
		flat closure		curved closure		flat closure		curved closure	
		Measured mean value [lm]	Uncertainty [lm]	Measured mean value [lm]	Uncertainty [lm]	Measured mean value [lm]	Uncertainty [lm]	Measured mean value [lm]	Uncertainty [lm]
Luminous flux	Whole space	8100	120	8400	130	6170	93	6490	97
	Half lower space	8100	120	8400	130	6160	92	6480	97
	Half upper space	1,16	0,02	5,78	0,09	8,7	0,1	13,7	0,2
	Spherical zone $88^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 90^\circ$	1,34	0,03	1,2	0,03	0,63	0,02	4,6	0,1
	Spherical zone $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 92^\circ$	0,41	0,01	0,82	0,02	0,42	0,01	3,29	0,08
	Spherical zone $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 100^\circ$	0,75	0,01	2,57	0,05	1,07	0,02	8,3	0,2

It is clear that the upward luminous flux emitted by the luminaires (is lower than the total luminous flux reflected upwards by lighted surfaces (mean reflectance factor $0,07 \leq \rho \leq 0,45$ depending on the material): the reflections always prevail, so it is better to use luminaires with the highest q_{inst} available.

A previously carried out research [15] considered the upward emission from a single installed luminaire and from a lighting plant. The research demonstrated that considering installations of a single luminaire, so the performances of the luminaire only, the most significant differences are due to the source and not to the closure (flat or curved glass): in fact LED luminaires emits upward 13% less flux than metal halide

luminaires.

Considering, instead, a lighting plant composed by several luminaires, the differences in the upward emitted flux due also to the luminaire closure, and not only to the source, are significant: in this case an interesting parameter is the installed flux normalized to implant length. In this case a dedicated geometrical reference system, similar to CIE C_γ system, was defined: the origin is on the road surface at the intersection of plane passing through the photometric centre of the luminaire and the road longitudinal axis and C_γ angles follows the CIE definition. The upward emitted flux is identified with angles $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 180^\circ$. Because the origin is on the road surface and not on the luminaires, as in the CIE C_γ reference system, some small differences between γ angles of the two reference system can arrive: considering a distance of 2 km (typical of road lighting installation and design) the difference is about $0,3^\circ$. In this case is clear the advantage of using LED luminaires with curved closure the differences, normalized to the upward emitted flux per kilometre of Metal Halide flat closure lighting plant are in

Table 8 Normalized upward luminous flux per kilometre of installation

Parameter	Metal Halide		LED	
	flat closure	curved closure	flat closure	curved closure
	Calculated value [-]	Calculated value [-]	Calculated value [-]	Calculated value [-]
Upward normalized luminous flux per kilometre of installation	1	0,9	0,9	0,775

5 CONCLUSIONS

This report considers the application of SSL in outdoor lighting. Available documents for outdoor lighting do not provide special indications for use of SSL, nor requirements that can arise to limitation in the use of SSL.

Road lighting is the most promising field for SSL applications, because its large diffusion, electrical consumptions and possibilities to take advantages of SSL, not only because its favourable S/P ratio (that is analysed in D4.3.4 and 5.1.5). Luminaires equipped with SSL showed the best luminance factor, a parameter able to evaluate the consumption optimization (high luminance factor means high luminance with less illuminance on road surface, so higher performances in terms of luminaires and implant design), but also lower upward flux (because with SSL is possible a better design and optical optimization of the luminaire), both performance are improved in the case of luminaire with curved closure equipped with SSL.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] Energy efficiency status report, JRC Scientific and politics report, European Community, 2012
 - [2] ENEA research http://www.enea.it/it/Ricerca_sviluppo/documenti/ricerca-di-sistema-elettrico/illuminazione-pubblica/18a-pres.-lumiere.pdf
 - [3] IEC 62471:2006/CIE S 009:2006 Photobiological safety of lamps and lamp systems, IEC
 - [4] EN 62471:2008, Photobiological Safety of lamps and lamp systems
 - [5] IES Position Statement PS–03-10, Effects of exterior lighting on human health, 2010
 - [6] CIE 1993, CIE 94:1993 Guide for Floodlighting, Vienna: CIE
 - [7] CIE 2010, CIE 190:2010 Mesopic vision, Vienna: CIE
 - [8] Draft of CIE 144 CIE xxx, CIE 144:xxx, 144 Road surface and road marking reflection characteristics, Vienna: CIE
 - [9] EN13201-4:2003, Light and lighting, Road lighting, Methods of measuring lighting performances
 - [10] PrEN13201-5, Light and lighting, Road lighting, Energy performances
 - [11] P. Iacomussi, G. Rossi, P. Soardo, The luminance coefficient in road lighting. A parameter to save energy and reducing atmospheric pollution, Proc. 11th Lux Europa Intl. Congress, Istanbul 9-11 September 2009, pp 647-652 and CD-ROM ISBN 978-9755613529
 - [12] Commission Regulation (EC) 245/2009 implementing Directive 2005/32/EC
 - [13] CIE 1997, CIE 126:1997 Guidelines for minimizing sky glow, Vienna: CIE
 - [14] CIE 2003, CIE 150:2003 Guide on the limitation of the effects of obstrusive light from outdoor lighting installations, Vienna: CIE
 - [15] G. Rossi, P. Iacomussi, G. Scialpi, Ricerca sistema Elettrico, ENEA, Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico, Caratterizzazione di impianti di illuminazione ai fini della valutazione della luce dispersa verso l'alto, Report RSE/10
- Berman, S.M., Jewett, D.L. et al. 1986. Pupillary size differences under incandescent and high pressure sodium lamps. Journal of the Illuminating Engineering Society, vol 16, pag 20
- [16] Rossi L., Zegna L., Iacomussi P., Rossi G., Pupil Size under different illuminant, CIE Proceedings on Lighting Quality and energy efficiency, Hangzhou, China, Sept. 2012